

Table 9: NVivo Code Book

Code Name	Description
1. Intra-Institutional Logics	Codes related to the various institutional logics.
a. Fiduciary Logics	Statements from participants that exemplify the influence of Fiduciary Logics.
i. Ethics Compromise	Issues/behaviors that exemplify when or how the ethics of advisors are compromised.
b. Sales Logics	Statements that are associated with Sales Logics.
i. Aggressive targets	Passages that relate to behavior influenced by aggressive sales targets.
ii. Pressure from clients	Passages that exemplify behavior or expressions of concern where pressure from clients is the cause.
iii. Pressure from FCs	Passages that identify how behavior is influenced because of pressure advisors feel from Financial Consultants.
c. Service Logics	Statements that reflect an association with Service Logics.
2. Self-Determination Theory	Codes associated with self-determination theory.
a. Extrinsic Motivation	Statements associated with extrinsic motivation.
b. Intrinsic Motivation	Statements associated with intrinsic motivation.
c. Professional Autonomy	Statements associate with professional autonomy.
i. Required (but perfunctory) activity.	Quantity over quality: The question becomes not, Did you create quality financial plans? Rather, How many financial plans did you create? This has to do with both service and professionalism. But hews most closely with professionalism.
3. Wellbeing	Codes related to the wellbeing of advisors or clients.
a. Advisor Wellbeing	Statements associated with advisor wellbeing.
b. Client Wellbeing	Passages associated with client wellbeing.
4. Advisor satisfaction with the organization	Passages associated with positive feelings about the organization.